

THE HISTORY OF THE MADRASAH OF THE FERGANA REGION (THE SECOND HALF OF THE XIXTH CENTURY – THE BEGINNING OF THE XXTH CENTURY)

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Annotation. In work are researched questions of the condition of the and madrassa in Fergana valley after conquest Turkestan Tsarist Russia, social-economic conditions, taught sciences, attitude to colonial administration to sphere of the enlightenment.

Keywords: tsarism, Fergana valley, schools, madrassa, scholastic process, study of the sciences, level to literacy, amount of the schools and madrassa.

Science and culture have long developed in this space connecting East and West and where great civilizations meet, and have had a strong influence on the science and development of other peoples. It is known that the Central Asian region, in particular, our ancestors made a unique contribution to the development of world civilizations in different periods of history.

In particular, in the second half of the XIX century, only in the Fergana Valley there were many schools, madrasas and houses in which there was a kind of education system, educational activities were conducted. For example, the Russians who took their first step into this country knew about the literacy of the inhabitants of the country and the high level of desire for education here.

In this place, Academician A., who visited the Fergana Valley in 1878, The proof of our opinion is Meddendorf's recognition that "the level of literacy of the country should be shown as an example to representatives of Russia engaged in public education" [3,P.62].

It can be noted that along with the madrasas founded in the ancient Middle Ages, there is some evidence in the country that new madrasas were built and put into operation on the eve of the occupation of the Russian Empire and during the occupation period, and shows that love has not faded. K.E. Bendrikov's information about this can fully substantiate our opinion. He reports: "Madrasas were opened in Ferghana-Andijan County: in Karasuva in 1862, in Karachinka, Kokankishlak, in 1865 in Sozok, in 1860 in Toshkichik, Uzgan, in Khayrabad in 1841. Kokand County: new madrasahs were built in Kashkar, Khojimat Vali madrasah, Turki madrasahs in Buwayda, Isfara and Rishtan. New madrassas were opened in Vodil, Guva, Yakkatut, Asak, Uchkurgan, Chinyon and Shakhrikhan of Margilan county. New madrasas were also built in the villages of Koson-Torakorgon, Chust, Yangikurgan of Namangan county.

Madrasas were established in Bulakbashi in 1759 and in Khojaabad in 1879[1, P.75].

In their works, these authors presented certain data on the economic savings, income and endowment properties of madrasahs, and based on these opinions, one can judge the achievements and shortcomings of a particular madrasah, as well as the level of quality of pedagogical work. determined. If the madrasah has a large income, it means that the educational process has been adjusted and organizational issues have been resolved correctly. The main thing is that the wealthy part of the people, in addition to sending their children to education, donated their personal income to such madrassas that came to the attention of the population. Count K.K. Palen's information deserves attention. If you look at pages 120-121 of his audit report, you can see a reasoned opinion and evidence of the material condition of the madrasah. In it, the author provides the following information.

According to the audit of the 1891-1892 academic year, there were 124 madrassas in the Fergana region. Of these, 95 are located in cities and 29 in villages. After the capture of Fergana by the Russians, 6 madrassas were opened. In this region, most madrassas receive donations from the wealthy part of the population in addition to donations. In general, the total average annual income of the madrasah of Fergana is determined by -149,797 soums, 12 madrasahs have an income of more than 2,000 soums, and 13 madrasahs - from 1,000 to 2,000 soums. Fifteen madrasahs have no charitable property or income at all.

In 1902, the chief inspector of educational institutions of the country wrote to the Ministry of Education more satisfactory reviews of the methods of the educational system of schools and madrassas. In particular, the letter contains the following points: "... Muslims receive education in their own schools and madrasas, as well as the European part of Russia, Siberia... Schools and madrassas play an important role in the life of the people and set certain directions for the younger generation...

Madrassas were considered higher educational institutions, and since they produced intellectuals of their time, their activities were always monitored. The evidence shows that our ancestors were completely illiterate, as some Soviet historians say. The country consistently continues the tradition of teaching specific techniques. At the moment, it should be recognized that an educational system based on the requirements of the development of world science has not been created in this area and advanced experience has not been fully mastered.

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